

Polyaniline/Phenol-Divinylbenzene Resin for CFRP Composite with Enhanced Electrical and Mechanical Properties

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ABSTRACT

This work focuses on the properties of the Polyaniline/Phenol-Divinylbenzene resins. Two different types of phenolic resins have been studied in this work as the modifiers of the polyaniline/divinylbenzene resin. DC conductivity measurement was utilized to evaluate the electrical properties of the resin composites. The flexural test was conducted to evaluate the mechanical properties of the resin and its potential application to prepare carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). Rheology study was conducted to investigate the room temperature stability of the resin for better impregnation of carbon fibers. Threefold enhancement in electrical conductivity was observed with the addition of phenolic resin with PANI/DBSA/DVB system.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thanks to their outstanding properties in many aspects, Carbon fiber reinforced plastics are already widely being used in the aerospace industry. A lightning strike on an aircraft is a relatively common phenomenon. Damage caused by a lightning strike can range from no damage to very serious ones and requires extensive repairs, which can take the airplane out of service for an extended period of time. Current solutions of lightning strike protection (LSP) using the metal foil, metal mesh and sometimes metallic coating on CF. Advantage of the metal-based method is their high electrical and thermal conductivities. High integration cost of metal mesh, galvanic corrosion, and extra weight compared to pure CFRP are the main drawbacks of the metal-based LSPs.

Intrinsically conductive polymers (ICPs) have been studied for many years, and their potential use in CFRP is a very promising solution for lightning strike protection. Among all ICPs, research of polyaniline (PANI) based electrically conductive composites is one of the most promising fields. Research on PANI has been well promoted in recent years due to its easy preparation, low cost, excellent electrical properties, and environmental stability [1]. Previous research in the author's group investigated a composite resin system with a Dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA) doped PANI combined with a crosslinking vinyl monomer divinylbenzene (DVB) [2]. The doping/semi-doping mechanism, electrical and mechanical properties and the thermal stability of the said resin had been well studied [3]. PANI/DBSA/DVB resin based CFRP was also fabricated. The preparation, conductivity, and lighting damage suppression property were investigated in details[4], [5].

Although the investigation of conductive CFRP was well carried out, there still has a de-doping problem caused by the proton extracting divinylbenzene monomer, resulting in an irreversible reduction in the conductivity. The full potential of PANI-based conductive composites is still not realized due to the de-doping phenomenon of PANI.

Therefore, a combination of phenolic resins was introduced with PANI/DBSA/DVB system to prepare a new conductive composite. Mori et al. reported that the phenol-DVB complex could be polymerized catatonically in the presence of protonic acid such as dodecylbenzene sulfonic acid (DBSA) or camphor sulfonic acid (CSA) without any additional catalyst [6]. The plausible curing mechanism of phenol-DVB in the presence of protonic acid is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The plausible curing mechanism of phenol-DVB in the presence of protonic acid.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Polyaniline (PANI) in emeraldine base form supplied by Regulus Co. Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan) has been used without special treatment. Dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA) was obtained from Kanto Chemical Co. Inc. (Tokyo, Japan). Divinylbenzene (DVB) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (St. Louis, USA).

Two different kinds of phenolic resins were used in this study. KAYAHARD GPH-65 was supplied by Nippon Kayaku Co. Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan), which is in solid flake state. MEH-8005 obtained from MEIWA Co. Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan), which is a liquid type phenolic resin.

2.2 Specimen Preparation

Specimens were prepared via a two-steps manufacturing. PANI and DBSA were mixed via centrifugal mixer in the ratio of 30:70 by weight percentage. Semi-doping was processed by keeping the complex in the oven at 60°C for 4 hours. DVB and phenol were mixed in advance via a centrifugal mixer. Two complexes were further mixed via a centrifugal mixer to get a homogeneous resin. The manufacturing process is shown in Figure 2. Three different resin will be coded as PDD, PDD-G65, and PDD-M8005, which corresponded to pure PANI/DBSA/DVB resin and two other resins modified by phenolic resins, as shown in Table 1. This nomenclature will be followed hereafter in this paper. The resin was then cured in the mold using a hot press machine at 130°C under 3MPa pressure for 1 hour.

Figure 2. The manufacturing process of the phenol-modified PANI/DBSA/DVB resin

	PANI (wt %)	DBSA (wt %)	DVB (wt %)	GPH-65 (wt %)	MEH-8005 (wt %)
PDD	9	21	70	-----	-----
PDD-G65	9	21	40	30	-----
PDD-M8005	9	21	40	-----	30

Table 1. Variation in weight ratios and phenolic-resin with a fixed amount of PANI/DBSA

2.3 Characterization

Specimens were polished into a uniform dimension, and electrodes were applied with silver adhesive on the side surface. Electrical resistance was measured via 3522-50LCR meter (Histester, Hioki E.E. Corporation, Ueda, Japan) with a constant voltage of 1V. The mechanical property was investigated by a 3-point bending test (ASTM D790-03) via an Instron-5582 UTM machine. Rheology was studied via a Viscometer TV-25 Type H (Toki Sangyo co. Ltd.).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Electrical properties

The electrical conductivity is the most important electrical property for all intrinsic conductive polymers. For our research purpose, the enhancement in conductivity is the priority in this study. The conductivity was calculated by the following equations:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{L}{R \times A} \quad (1)$$

Where the R stands for the resistance measured via LCR meter, and the A and L stand for the cross-sectional area and the length of the specimens, respectively. The results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure.3 The electrical conductivity of resin composites.

In this research, the PANI content was strictly controlled to study the influence of two different phenolic resin. Low PANI content resulted in a relatively low conductivity of pure PDD composite compared to our previous study[2]. However, we can easily see that with the addition of phenolic resin, there are 3-3.5 times improvements in electrical conductivity. We assume that this enhancement is because of the reduced de-doping effect introduced by phenolic resin. As we mentioned in advance, the plausible curing mechanism of phenol-DVB in the presence of protonic acid is a cationic polymerization forming a crosslinking network. The presence of phenolic resin suppresses the cationic scavenging of DVB monomer, resulted in the reduce of de-doping during the curing process. The conductivity enhancement of these two phenolic resins is in the same ratio, which might indicate that the improvement of conductivity in these cases is mainly because of the reduced de-doping effect of phenolic resin.

3.2 Mechanical properties

Another criterion in evaluating resin composite for CFRP is mechanical properties. For CFRP application in the future, fractural properties were studied through a 3-point bending test instead of a tensile test. The results are shown in Figure 4. Obviously, with the addition of phenolic resin, the flexural modulus and strength were all increased. It is probably due to the crosslinking structure formed by the reaction between DVB and phenol units in the resin.

Figure 4. Flexural modulus(A) and strength(B) of resin composites.

Introducing polymer chains with a much higher molecular weight not only reducing the de-doping phenomenon, which leads to a relatively higher percentage cure but also improving the mechanical strength of the composites. The mechanical properties follow the same trend as the electrical conductivity. However, the G65 gives a much better enhancement in modulus and strength compared to the M8005. It is maybe because of the different molecular structures of the resin, which affect the natural properties of the resin products.

3.3 Rheology

Rheology study is also important in this research since the final goal of this intrinsic conductive polymer resin is CFRP application. Initiate viscosity and the stability in room temperature determine the impregnating of the resin into CF bundles and the manufacturing time limitation. Viscosity measurement results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Viscosities of resin composites.

The PDD resin system is one of an ideal resin for CFRP impregnation and fabrication because of the good stability in room temperature and very low initial viscosity. However, when modified with G65, the initial viscosity became undesirable high (up to 8000mPa·s), which would be a huge problem of impregnation when applied on CF. Moreover, the later increasing speed of the viscosity indicates the inapplicable on CFRP. On the other hand, the increasing speed of viscosity and the initiate viscosity in PD-M8005-D case show higher potential in impregnation and processing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, three PANI/DBSA/DVB based resins have been successfully prepared and carefully investigated, two of which were modified with different kind of phenolic resins. Electrical conductivity, mechanical property, and the rheology property were carefully studied. General enhancement on electrical conductivity and mechanical property were achieved by the introduction of phenolic resins. Resins modified with G65 achieved 0.26S/cm electrical conductivity with a PANI content of 9 wt%, 260% improvement compared to the non-modified subject. Furthermore, better mechanical properties and conductivity compared to the resin modified with M8005 can be observed. However, the initiate viscosity of G65 modified resin is too high for impregnation, and later increasing speed indicates the fast curing, which leads to a difficulty in further application. Although M8005 gave less enhancement on both conductivity (220%) and mechanical property (12%), the viscosity is easier for CF fabric impregnation, and the further increasing rate is more suitable for the manufacturing process.

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